

Stubble Burning: Its Impact on the Ecosystem Anushka Sadana

ABSTRACT

Stubble burning has emerged as a leading cause of deteriorating air and soil quality, especially in South Asia and particularly in Indo-gangetic plains of Northern India. This is mainly attributed to the intense rice - wheat rotation system of farming, which generates large amounts of stubble. The practice of stubble burning is a source of gaseous pollutants such as CO₂, CO, Nitrous oxides, Sulphur oxides and methane, as well as particulate matter (PM₁₀ & PM_{2.5}), causing serious damage to human health and the environment. Human health gets globally affected in varying severity.

The organ systems mainly affected are respiratory and cardiovascular. Beside these, ailments affecting skin, eyes are also observed. The respiratory system ailments include Asthma, COPD, Allergic Bronchitis, Emphysema and Interstitial Lung diseases. Long-term exposure to pollutants can cause reduction in life expectancy. Burning of the stubble in the fields, destroys the nutrient value of the soil. The heat generated from stubble burning penetrates into the soil down to earth elevating the temperature to 33.8 to 42.5 degrees Celsius. This kills the useful bacteria and fungal populations critical for a fertile soil. Burning of crop residue causes damage to microbes present in the upper layer of soil, as well as in the organic quality.

KEYWORDS: Stubble Burning, Pollution, Impact, Soil Pollution, Respiratory Illnesses

INTRODUCTION

The aim of this research paper is to comprehensively review the existing literature and current status of stubble burning in India including

1. How the stubble is generated and burnt?
2. What is the composition of emissions from stubble burning?
3. The impact of stubble burning on human health and Ecosystem.
4. Alternative methods of managing stubble to prevent the damaging effects on human health and environment.

Stubble burning has been defined as the burning of stubbles by farmers after harvesting of crops. Stubbles are the cut stalks left on the field after the grains such as rice and wheat have been harvested. This agriculture practice has both **positive and negative consequences**.

ADVANTAGES

- Cheaper and easier.
- Helps to comb out weeds and pests.
- Can reduce nitrogen tie-up.

DISADVANTAGES

- Loss of nutrients.
- Pollution from smoke including greenhouse gases and others that damage the ozone layer.
- Risk of fires spreading out of control.

The common farming system in the Indo-Gangetic Plains (**IGP**) is the rice-wheat rotation system. IGP is a region in South Asia blessed with fertile agricultural land and diverse

ecosystems. Geographically, it occupies 20% of India's land area and 40% of the country's population. Most of the farmers in this region use combine harvesters for harvesting grains. This machine performs different tasks that are Reaping, Winnowing and Threshing into a single operation. Although very efficient they generate a huge amount of stubble consisting of stocks 15 cm high. Major proportion of stubble generated is burnt on the fields of Haryana and Punjab two of key agricultural States contribute to 48% of stubble burning. The burning takes place in April-May (after wheat harvesting) and in October-November (after rice harvesting).

Why do farmers Resort to stubble burning?

- It is an easy method to prepare the farmland for next sowing. (rice or wheat as the case may be).
- Average time interval between the harvest of rice and sowing of wheat is about 15 days and the time interval between sowing of kharif crops after (mainly paddy) harvesting of wheat is about 45 days.

What are the Meteorological factors which act synergistically with stubble burning to deteriorate air quality?

Across the Indo gangetic Plains of North India, many meteorological factors contribute in further damaging the air quality along with stubble burning. Conditions such as ambient temperature, relative humidity, wind speed, wind direction and air pressure play an important role. Hence the effect of stubble burning is a more severe postharvest station of rice as the low winter temperature leads to a more stable atmosphere. Hence, the pollutants stay longer in the atmosphere during this time creating a very harsh level of pollution. The atmospheric conditions provide greater residing time for pollutants, poor depression and lesser rate of smoke diffusion. This accumulation exerts more damaging effects on the environment.

LITERATURE REVIEW

- Pratika and Sandhu, 2020.
- Ghai and Sane, 2018.
- Krishna et Al, 2011.
- Kapil, 2019.
- Sharma et Al, 2010.
- Ravinder et Al, 2019.

BACKGROUND

The Green Revolution was a period that began in the 1960s during which agriculture was converted into a modern industrial system by the adoption of technology such as use of High Yield Variety (HYV) seeds, mechanised farm tools, pesticides, irrigation facilities and fertilisers.

[The Green Revolution in India led to an increase in food grain production in Punjab, Haryana and Western Uttar Pradesh.]

Despite the initial prosperity experienced in these states, the Green Revolution caused serious Environmental damages.

- Excessive and inappropriate use of fertilisers and pesticides polluted waterways and killed beneficial insects and wildlife.
- It has caused overuse of soil and rapidly depleted its nutrients.
- Rampant irrigation practices led to eventual soil degradation and fall in underground waterlands at many places.
- Heavy dependence on a few major crops (wheat and paddy) has led to loss of

- biodiversity.
- Increased cases of stubble burning since 1980.

Use of advanced farming equipment played a significant role in the Green Revolution. The use of the modern combine harvester, a versatile machine designed to harvest a variety of grain crops, started during the Green Revolution and it still continues to be used widely. It combines four separate harvesting operations - Reaping, Threshing, Gathering and Winnowing into a single process.

Although combine harvesters are the most important labour sowing equipment, they leave a significant amount of strain (**stubble**) on the fields. This leftover straw is burnt by the farmers to rapidly prepare the fields for the next crop. This stubble burning is responsible for the deteriorating air quality and increase in respiratory ailments. Burning of rice straw every year is the source of greenhouse gases like Carbon Dioxide, CH₄ responsible for depletion of ozone layer.

Stubble Burning and Pandemic

The stubble burning is set to make Covid-19 far deadlier, covid-19 and air pollution are a dangerous combination. Air pollution causes damage and inflammation in lungs and other body tissues, reducing the body's ability to resist the virus which may result in a more severe form of infection.

Stubble Burning led to Mucormycosis during the pandemic. A research conducted by the department of infections diseases and infection control of the university of Texas MD Anderson Cancer Centre revealed that MM causing fungal spores spread mainly through fumes from the burning of **Mucorales rich biomass** including cow dung and crop stubble.

DISCUSSION

GENERATION OF CROP STUBBLE AND BURNING

After the Green Revolution, India became self-sufficient in food grains. As a result of boost received by the use of HYV seeds, modern farming equipment, use of pesticides and fertilisers, production of wheat and rice increased by many folds, as a consequence of

increased production of these crops, a huge amount of waste is generated after their harvesting. This farm waste is mainly in the form of stubble (**in case of wheat and rice**) and leaves (**after sugarcane**).

This waste is used as animal feed, making cattle sheds, as raw materials for small scale industries such as prep/board industries, biogas generation. Nevertheless, a significant portion of the stubble is left on the field with no specific utility and it is burnt to clear the farm for next crop.

Roughly about 400 mt. of agricultural stubble is generated each year by cereal crops out of which 22% and 34% are contributed by wheat and rice stubbles respectively. The maximum stubble is generated by cereal crops constituting about 58% of the total annual crop production. For most of the crops, the amount of stubble generated is higher than the grain produced. In the case of rice and wheat, the stubble is 1.5 times the grain produced. In Punjab, more than 90% of the farmers burn their stubble in the field. Since the majority of the farmers in this region practice mechanised farming, a large quantity of stubble is generated. The stubbles are in the form of straw, stalk and sugarcane leaves.

Despite a ban being imposed on stubble burning by various state pollution control boards, farm fires continue unabated. Satellite fire hotspots have shown an increased occurrence of agricultural fires. **Thumaty et al 2015** used **MODIS** satellite data and observed continuous occurrence of fire in about 60% of total agricultural areas in Punjab and Haryana.

EMISSION COMPOSITION

Stubble Burning is a significant source of Carbon dioxide, volatile organic compounds, nitrogen oxides and hydrocarbons accounting for 10% of the emissions of the world. Emissions contain particulate matter and harmful gases such as SO₂, NO₂, N₂O, CO, CO₂ and CH₄, all of which severely affect human health. **Sahai et al 2011** gathered that upon burning 63 Mt of the stubble, 3.4 Mt of CO, 0.1 Mt of NO₂, 91 Mt of CO₂, 0.6 Mt of CH₄ and 1.2 Mt of particulate matter are emitted.

The smoke particles generated during stubble burning are reported to be of different particle sizes depending on the combustion phase. For example, smoke particles released during the smouldering phase were reported to be coarser than those released during the flaming phase. (**Ordou & Agranovski, 2019**). **Wardoyo et al 2007** investigated the size distribution of smoke particles in varying burning modes for some species of grass and found out that the emitted smoke particles range in diameter between (30 nm and 60 nm) for **Flaming phase** and around (60 nm and 210 nm) for **Smouldering Phase**.

TRANSPORT AND DISPERSION OF STUBBLE BURNING EMISSIONS

The resultant emissions can travel a very long range in the air via complex atmospheric processes determined by the prevailing meteorological conditions (**Ghosh et al, 2019**). Air quality is significantly affected by the regional transport of the pollutants across the state and national boundaries. Studies show that the pollutants travel from the Punjab region of India to Pakistan and vice versa. (**Ghosh et al 2019, Shabir et al 2019**.)

EFFECT OF STUBBLE BURNING ON ECOSYSTEM

Burning of stubble poses a serious threat to the air quality of the exposed environment. **Kaskaoutis et al 2014** pointed out that the air quality is considerably affected by agricultural burning due to the emission of aerosol and gaseous pollutants. PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ are reported to have the highest effect on the health of the exposed population. Despite not being the main source of pollution, stubble burning is a significant source of air pollution in India. A combination of point and nonpoint sources constitute the composite emissions, these sources include industries, power plants, vehicles, construction and indoor emissions (**sharma and dhiskir 2016**). **Guttikunda and Gurjar 2012** found that emissions from industrial sources comprise 15% of CO, 14% of PM_{2.5}, while transport emissions contain 17% of PM_{2.5}, 13% of PM₁₀, 53% of NO₂ and 18% of CO. On the other hand, stubble burning emissions are relatively lower, comprising 14% of CO and 12% PM_{2.5}.

The air quality becomes austere mostly in November of each year across the North Indian states. The air quality of urban areas is more affected by stubble burning emissions because of the presence of accumulated pollutants from vehicular and industrial emissions leading to severe air quality. (**Mishra, 2019**).

EFFECT ON SOIL FERTILITY

Apart from the effects on air quality, stubble burning also affects soil productivity by burning the essential nutrients inside the soil. (**Singh et al, 2018**). It also raises the soil temperature to about 42 degree Celsius, thus displacing or killing the important microorganisms in the soil at a depth of 2.5 cm (**Jain et al, 2014**). This generates an additional expense of regaining back the soil fertility through the application of fertiliser or compost. Stubble burning strips the soil of the essential nutrients i.e. Nitrogen, Phosphorus and Potassium (**NPK**) as well as other micronutrients. For instance, the burning of rice stubble leads to loss of about 0.445 Mt. of NPK, 0.144 Mt. in the case of

wheat stubble burning.

AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY

Stubble burning is an important source of various pollutants such as sulphur dioxide, NO₂. These pollutants may affect agricultural productivity directly or indirectly (**Satesh et al, 2020**). Air pollution poses risks on yield of crops depending on the emission pattern, atmospheric transport, leaf uptake and on plants' biochemical defence capacity. **Direct effects** include injury to leaves, grains or assimilation of metals. Nitrogen Oxide can damage the plant tissue and cause discoloration. Sulphur Oxide may lead to the formation of acid rain which has severe effects on plants and soil and may lead to destruction of flora (**Augustraitis et al, 2010**). Prolonged exposure of plants to particulate matter may lead to Chlorosis and Necrosis (**Ghosh et al, 2019**).

Indirect effects include the provision of conducive conditions for growth of pests or discussions like growth of aphid pests is favoured by high concentrations of SO₂ and NO₂. Air pollutants produce reactive oxygen species (**ROS**) which adversely affect biochemical processors of plants and reduce their tolerance capacity to other stresses also (**Satesh et al**).

Several vital physiological processes such as photosynthesis, carbon dioxide fixation and energy metabolism are negatively affected by air pollutants. The magnitude of adverse effects caused by air pollutants depends on concentration, duration of exposure and combination of air pollutants (**Satesh et al**). Ozone is the most phytotoxic pollutant. Stubble burning releases Vols and NO_x which combine to form ground level ozone pressure of solar radiation. It affects plant metabolism and damages leaves causing serious damage to crops in the Northern parts of India (**Sharma et al, 2019**).

EFFECTS ON HUMAN HEALTH AND WELL BEING

India saw more than 23.5 lakh premature deaths due to pollution of all types in 2019, the highest among all countries globally. This is one of the key takeaways of a new study published in **Lancet Planetary Health Journal**.

- **16.7 lakh: Fatalities caused by air pollution**
- **9.8 lakh: deaths due to PM 2.5 pollutant**
- **6.1 lakh: casualties caused by household air pollution**

The figure below shows the pollution in Delhi before and after Stubble Burning periods-

A

B

Causes-

- Burning of biomass in households.
- Coal Combustion.
- Crop Burning.

Most affected areas

In India, air pollution is most severe in the Indo-Gangetic plain (**Northern India**) where topography and meteorology concentrate pollution from energy, mobility, industry, agriculture and other activities.

Economic impact

Economic losses due to modern forms of pollution such as ozone pollution has increased between 2000 and 2019 in India and are now approximately 1% of its GDP. The harmful effects of exposure to air pollution range from skin and eye irritation to severe neurological, cardiovascular and respiratory disorders. It may also lead to lethal effects especially when the exposed victim is having pre-existing respiratory problems (**Saggn et al 2018**). In chronic cases, exposure to high levels of air pollution may cause permanent health injuries such as development of lung diseases, asthma, COPD, bronchitis, cancer and emphysema (**Ghosh et al, 2019**). Most of the farmers exposed to stubble smoke complain about eye and lung irritation (**Kumari et al, 2015**).

Fine particulate matter PM 2.5 has more effect on humans than the larger sizes as it can penetrate deeper into the respiratory system. Its effects range from running nose, coughing and difficulty in breathing to chronic effects such as asthma. Effects are more profound in children due to the weak immune system. Other effects of exposure to pollution include stroke, tuberculosis, lung cancer and pneumonia.

CONCLUSION

The large-scale wheat-rice crop rotation system practised in India has resulted in the generation of significant quantities of crop stubble of-ten more than the quantity of grains harvested. A considerable portion of these stubbles is usually burnt on-field to clear the farm for next planting, thus releasing toxic pollutants to the atmosphere which leads to the deterioration of air quality. It may be concluded (on the basis of existing evidence) that the combined efforts of stubble burning emissions and meteorological conditions are the cause of severity of air quality especially during rice stubble burning episodes in North Indian cities.

The pollutants from stubble burning pose a grave risk to the health of the exposed population as they are linked to several health and issues and even death, in severe cases. In addition to atmospheric pollution, stubble burning may also lead to climate change, global warming and the destruction of soil nutrients. It is, therefore, the need of the hour to implement exhaustive policies to curb this menace at its base.

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